

Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Leverage of Non-Financial Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchanges

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Helen Wairimu**- Department of Finance and Accounting-School of Business University of Nairobi ⁽²⁾**Prof. Willy Muturi** -Department of Accounting Economics and Finance School of Business -Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology ⁽³⁾**Oluoch Oluoch**-Department of Business Administration-School of Business -Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

Abstract

Listed and non-listed institutions are always in need of finances geared towards enhancing their firm performance which has a pivotal role in the relationship they will enjoy internally and externally. The ability of an organization to invest borrowed capital on projects with a higher return on investment has a significant impact on shareholders wealth maximization. Panel regression modelling revealed the positive influence of firm size and profitability and inverse influence of tangibility and growth opportunities on the leverage of listed non-financial companies in Nairobi securities exchanges.

Key Words: Financial characteristics, Firm size, Profitability, Tangibility, Growth opportunities.

Introduction

Listed and non-listed institutions are always in need of finances geared towards enhancing their firm performance which has a pivotal role on the relationship they will enjoy internally and externally (Ezeoha, 2008; Hasannejadneisi, Mazraeh & Mousavi, 2013). During credit evaluations, financial institutions should endeavor to finance those companies with sufficient collateral security and large firms with huge sales and high profits since they have lower chances of bankruptcy and financial distress and have diversified their investment portfolio as compared to smaller companies (Hasannejadneisi *et al.*, 2013). Empirical examination showed that firm characteristics have either a positive or negative influence on its stakeholders. Moreover, with recent globalization, trends both local and multinational companies have continuously expanded their sizes, profitability, operating cash flow and growth opportunities as an indication of corporate roles which they have to play and hence the benefits accrued from increased size and profitability (Ezeoha, 2008).

Firm financial characteristics are those unique features which are used to differentiate one firm from another (Wahome *et al.*, 2015). Firm characteristics have not only gained currency value externally but also have impacted on internal stakeholders (Ezeoha, 2008). Indeed, these attributes are the yardsticks against which companies are evaluated during credit appraisal. A Chinese case of private companies has shown a positive and significant relationship between firm characteristics and external financing. As the firm size increases, there are more prospects for superior performance due to elaborate mechanisms for working capital management. This ultimately lowers borrowing costs and increases both short- and long-term liabilities (Ikechukwu & Madubuko, 2016).

Although manufacturing companies listed in Nigeria have adopted the use of leverage there is need to exercise caution since it has a negative influence on financial performance (Iorpev & Kwanum, 2012). These findings were contrasted by Ogbulu and Emenei (2012) who recommended that corporate decision makers should deploy more long-term debt than equity in their financing since it has a positive and significant influence on firm value. A South African case by Gwatidzo and Ojah, (2009) reported an inverse relationship between profitability and leverage amongst listed companies in South Africa. An examination of leverage in the insurance sector in Ethiopia was brought forth by Getahun (2014) in Ethiopia. The study found that 52% of the insurance finance was raised through debt financing. In addition, leverage was negatively influenced by growth opportunities, firm size, operating cash flows and business risk and it had positively impacted by tangibility.

Chesang and Ayuma (2016) reported inverse and significant relationship between profitability and leverage for listed agricultural companies at the NSE. Findings by Gathogo and Ragui (2014) reported a positive and insignificant relationship between growth opportunities and leverage for non-listed small and microenterprises in Kenya. Githira and Nasieku (2015) reported a positive insignificant relationship between growth, profitability

and firm size and capital structure while asset structure was reported to have an inverse relationship for firms quoted in the East African Securities Exchange. Tarus, Chenous, and Biwott (2014) reported inverse significant relation between liquidity and leverage for Kenyan listed firms. There are anticipated variations on the effect of firm characteristics on leverage globally and locally owing to financial market development stages. Consequently, there was a need to empirically examine the influence of firm financial characteristics on the leverage of listed companies in Nairobi securities exchange. Specifically, the study sought:

- i. To determine the influence of tangibility of assets on the leverage of non-financial firms listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- ii. To find out the influence of growth opportunities on the leverage of non-financial listed firms at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- iii. To establish the influence of firm size on the leverage of non-financial firms listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- iv. To examine the influence of profitability on the leverage of non-financial firms listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- v. To evaluate the moderating effect of operating cash flows on the influence of financial characteristics on the leverage of non-financial firms listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange.

Literature Review

A Thailand case to investigate the determinants of capital structure was carried out by Thippayana (2014). Guided by Modigliani and Miller hypotheses, the trade off theory and pecking order theory the study postulated that leverage is determined by firm size, profitability, asset tangibility, growth opportunities, and business volatility risk. The panel research design was adopted and a sample of 144 listed companies from 2000 to 2011 was considered. Multiple linear regression analysis was applied to analyse the data. The study revealed a positive and significant relationship between firm size, tangibility, business volatility risk, and leverage while profitability had an inverse and significant relationship.

Handoo and Sharma (2014) investigated the determinants of the capital structure an Indian perspective. Through panel research design, a sample of 870 firms listed in India from 2001 to 2010. In the study capital, structured was deemed to be determined by profitability, tangibility, growth opportunities, and cost of debt, size, and financial distress, debt servicing capability, tax rate and age of a firm. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyse the data. Results of the study revealed a negative and significant relationship between tangibility of assets and both short term debt and total debt while it had a negative and insignificant relationship with long term debt.

Mahnazmahdavi et al. (2013) investigated the effect of sales growth on capital structure among companies which were listed in Tehran securities exchange. Judgmental sampling technique was used to select 60 companies and secondary data was collected over a four-year period. Regression analysis revealed a positive relationship between sales growth and leverage. These findings were in support of agency theory and those who were in charge of management had persistently ensured that optimal.

An investigation of the impact of financial market development on financial leverage on Chinese listed companies was carried out by Tai (2017). Purposive sampling was used to select 116 companies listed in Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange from 2009 to 2015. Generalized linear regression modeling revealed a positive and significant relationship between market capitalization and capital structure but the volume of shares traded revealed a negative and significant relationship with capital structure. Although these results mirrored market timing theory they contrasted signaling theory.

An investigation of the effect of capital structure on the financial performance of SMEs in Thika Sub County was carried out by Mwangi and Birundu (2015). Purposive sampling was used to select 40 SMEs which had been in operation for five years from 2009 to 2013. Multiple regression analysis revealed that capital structure had a positive and non-significant effect on financial performance while both asset turnover and asset tangibility had inverse and non-significant effect on financial performance. Since the data was a panel in nature it was

appropriate to carry out tests such as Hausman, serial autocorrelation test, multicollinearity, and stationarity test prior to fitting the regression model.

Badar and Saeed (2013) investigated the impact of capital structure on the financial performance of companies listed sugar sector in Pakistan. Purposive sampling was used to select 10 companies which were listed in the food sector from 2007 to 2011 at Karachi securities exchange. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the data and results of the study revealed a positive and insignificant relationship between short term debt and sales turnover. In contrast, there was a positive and significant relationship between long term debt and asset turnover. This finding reveals that most of the studies have adopted a conservative financing policy and they are mirroring agency theory.

In Kenya Chesang and Ayuma (2016) investigated the effect of profitability on the leverage of listed agricultural companies in NSE. The study adopted a descriptive research design to examine the effect of long-term debt, short term debt and equity on profitability. Regression analysis revealed an inverse significant relationship between financial leverage and profitability; these results were in support of pecking order theory and static trade off theory.

A study to investigate the impact of cash flow on capital structure among companies listed in Tehran securities exchange was carried out by Kordlouie, Mosadeg, and Rad, (2014). Multiple regression was used to analyze secondary data collected from 2006 to 2010. Simple random sampling was used to select 415 listed companies. Results of the study revealed a positive and significant relationship between operating cash flow and capital structure. The following relationship was conceptualized from the literature review.

Methodology

The study used panel data. Panel data is a series of multidimensional data where the behaviour of entities are observed over time (Wooldridge, 2002). The key advantage of panel data is the ability to allow the researcher to control for variables that are not observable or measurable like culture and management practices over time but not across entities (Wooldridge, 2002). It was obtained from the NSE handbooks and from specific companies' websites. As shown in the data collection sheet data on non-current assets, market prices, book value, turnover, total liabilities, profit after tax, operating cash flows were gathered. Secondary data was collected for period 2008-2016. Univariate and multivariate techniques were applied for data analysis. The influence was tested

through the use of regression analysis and moderation was examined through an examination of marginal changes of slope coefficients due to the introduction of operating cash flows. The general models were of the form:

$$L_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T_{i,t} + \beta_2 S_{i,t} + \beta_3 G_{i,t} + \beta_4 P_{i,t} + \epsilon_j \dots \dots \dots \text{Model 1}$$

The following regression model with the moderating variable was used for the analysis as proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986).

$$L_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T_{i,t} + \beta_2 S_{i,t} + \beta_3 G_{i,t} + \beta_4 P_{i,t} + \beta_5 CF_{i,t} + CF_{i,t}(\beta_6 T_{i,t} + \beta_7 S_{i,t} + \beta_8 G_{i,t} + \beta_9 P_{i,t}) + \epsilon_j \dots \dots \dots \text{Model 2}$$

Where

L_{it} - total liabilities/total assets for each firm i at time t

T = Tangibility of assets, G =Growth opportunities, S =Firm size, P = Profitability, CF =Operating cash flows, β_i ($i=0,1, 2, \dots, 9$) are the associated regression coefficients, ϵ_j is the associated error term.

Findings and Discussions

4.2 Overall Descriptive Statistics

As shown in Table 4.1, the average tangibility over the period was 58%. The minimum value was 0.05, the maximum value of 0.97, the standard deviation of 0.23 and coefficient of skewness of -0.36. These statistics imply that of the firms' total assets, more were non-current in nature with only 42% accounting for current assets. The negative skewness further reinforces this fact. This further indicates that were firms required to provide collaterals in terms of non-current assets, they would have been generally sound. With a minimal range and standard deviation, the investment in non-current assets looked stable.

The average firm size was 15.40 translating into approximately sh. 4.9 billion with a minimum of the natural logarithm of 11.13 (approximately sh. 68 million) and a maximum of the natural logarithm of 19.22 (approximately sh. 222 billion). The skewness was -0.12 and the standard deviation was 1.9. This show that generally firms were doing well in raising revenue with majority raising more than the average reported hence lying on the left tail of the distribution. Again, the fluctuations in revenue were not huge as evidenced by the standard deviation. The average profit after tax to total assets over the period was -0.35 minimum of -135.98 and maximum of 1.05 with a negative skewness of -18.40. The standard deviation of the profits after tax to assets distribution was 7.39. These results show that the majority of firms were not utilizing their assets properly to generate profits after tax, therefore, leaning on the left tail of the distribution. Comparing the sales and profits statistics, it appears that there was a problem in cost management since revenue generation was okay but profits after tax were dismal. This average negative profit performance is potentially dangerous to firms wishing to borrow for expansion.

The average operating cash flow to sales ratio was 16%, minimum being -7.94 and a maximum of 3.46. Skewness measure demonstrated a negative distribution. The standard deviation of the ratio distribution was 0.69. This shows that on average, from every shilling of revenue generated approximately sixteen cents went to cover operating expenses with a huge chunk left to financing and investment activities. Again, as evidenced by the standard deviation, the volatility of the revenue going to operating costs was relatively stable. The negative cash flow is an indicator that many firms were operating at the mercy of suppliers. The average growth opportunity was 1.58 with a minimum of -16.67, maximum of 55.56 and a positive distribution with a skewness coefficient of 7.88. The standard deviation of the growth opportunity distribution was 4.65. These statistics indicate that although generally firms' market values were better than their book values, in the majority of firms, market and book values were close and to the right of the distribution. High market to book value of firms is consistent with the market timing theory dictate. The average long-term debts to total assets were 18.31%. This shows that a large portion of firms' assets was financed with short term debt. This is consistent with Addae, Nyarko-Baasi, and Hughes (2013) who concluded that most of the listed companies in Ghana relied on short term debt to finance their enterprises. The maximum borrowing also reaffirms this position with short term debt to total assets ration being 1.29 and long term to total assets ratio being 1.13. It is also worth noting that some firms had no long-term debt at least once. As Mwangi (2016) posit, it could imply that short term debt financing was less costly compared to the long-term debt which is usually associated with high value

collateral and at times restrictive covenants to make it unattractive. A positive skewness in both long and short-term debts to total assets show that majority lied on the right tail of the distribution.

These findings contradict Mwangi, *et al.* (2014) who concluded that the majority of firms at the NSE use long term debt to finance their assets. The average debt financing to total assets of firms at the NSE over the period was 49% with a minimum of 0.1 and a maximum of 1.45. The distribution of total debt to assets is positively skewed showing that the majority of the firm's total debts to assets were to the right of the distribution. With 49% debt financing, it also implies that 51% of a firm's assets financing was through equity. This could indicate an aggressive strategy in listing by firms possibly due to the ease of listing requirements, tax advantages on listing among other benefits provided by the market regulator over time.

Table 4.1 Overall Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
T	339	0.05	0.97	0.58	0.23	-0.36	0.13
P	339	-135.98	1.05	-0.35	7.39	-18.40	0.13
S	339	11.13	19.22	15.40	1.91	-0.12	0.13
CF	339	-7.94	3.46	0.16	0.69	-4.92	0.13
G	338	-16.67	55.56	1.58	4.65	7.88	0.13
LTA	339	0.00	1.13	0.18	0.18	1.78	0.13
STA	339	0.01	1.29	0.30	0.19	0.84	0.13
DTA	339	0.01	1.45	0.49	0.23	0.91	0.13

4.2 Diagnostics Results

4.2.1 Auto Correlation for Non-financial Companies Listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in tables 4.2, models with LTA as the response variable had F statistics of 83.276, without cash flow moderation, and 103.976 with moderation. The p values for both were 0, which confirmed significance at 5 percent level of significance. This, therefore, implies the presence of serial correlation.

With the exception of one case where there was no autocorrelation, feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) method was used to overcome the challenge of serial correlation. FGLS is preferred since it guarantees the efficiency and consistency of the estimators. This guarantee in return ensures that the significance tests carried out are valid. According to Wooldridge (2002) and as cited by Mwangi (2016), FGLS is preferred to GLS since the true values of the variances and covariances for the error terms as used by the GLS estimator are unknown in reality and therefore the GLS estimator is not a feasible estimator. The following procedure for the FGLS technique whose resulting slopes (β_j) is consistent and efficient as provided by Wooldridge (2002) is adopted in the study. Regress Y on X_t and obtain the residuals U_t . Regress the residuals against lagged residuals, U_{t-1} to obtain the coefficients (ρ) of U_{t-1} . Use OLS equation on the following equation. $y_t = \beta_0 x_{t0} + \beta_1 x_{t1} + \beta_2 x_{t2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{tk} + e_t$. Where, $x_{t0} = (1-\rho)$ for $t \geq 2$ and $x_{10} = (1-\rho^2)^{1/2}$

Table 4.2 Wooldridge Test for Autocorrelation for Non-Financial Companies Listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange

Model	F (1, 41)	Prob>F
Without moderator	12.29	0.0011
With moderator	42.272	0.0000

4.2.2 Multicollinearity Test Statistics for Listed Non-Financial Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Table 4.3 presents the VIFs for the various study variables. The results indicate that the VIFs for all variables were less than 5 implying that the study data did not exhibit multicollinearity as recommended by Gujarati (2003). This guarantees the stability of the slopes and hence valid and robust significance tests (Schindler, 2008).

Table 4.3 Multicollinearity Test Statistics for Listed Non-Financial Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
CF	1.16	0.864814
T	1.07	0.934345
S	1.07	0.936916
G	1.06	0.941641
P	1.01	0.989481
Mean VIF	1.07	

4.2.3 Heteroscedasticity Test Results for Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Table 4.4 shows the likelihood ratio tests statistics. The null hypotheses of the tests were that the error variance was homoscedastic for each model. The likelihood-ratio tests produced chi-square values of 49.95 605.30 with p-values of 0.0000. This implies that the tests were significant at 5% level of significance hence the existence of heteroscedasticity in the study data (Gujarati, 2003). To remedy the problem, FGLS estimation technique was used (Wooldridge, 2002).

Table 4.4 Heteroscedasticity Test Results for Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Chi Square	Degree of freedom	p value
49.95	5	0.0000

4.2.4 Stationarity Test Results for Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As alluded to earlier, the panel unit root test was carried out to all variables used in order to avoid spurious regression results due to non-stationarity. The unit root test statistics are presented in Table 4.5. From the table, it is evident that all variables are stationary at the level since the null hypothesis that all variables are not stationary at 5% significant level is rejected. This is further assurance on the robustness of the expected results. Further on, there was no need to differentiate the data.

Table 4.5 Unit Root Test Results for Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable		Statistic	Value	p-value
T	Inverse chi-squared (84)	P	181.1602	0.0000
	Inverse normal	Z	-3.8778	0.0001
	Inverse logit t (199)	L*	-4.9053	0.0000
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	7.4961	0.0000
P	Inverse chi-squared (84)	P	199.0623	0.0000
	Inverse normal	Z	-4.9235	0.0000
	Inverse logit t (199)	L*	-5.9628	0.0000
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	8.8772	0.0000
G	Inverse chi-squared (84)	P	268.5958	0.0000
	Inverse normal	Z	-5.592	0.0000
	Inverse logit t (194)	L*	-9.7774	0.0000

CF	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	14.2419	0.0000
	Inverse chi-squared (78)	P	164.857	0.0000
	Inverse normal	Z	-6.1083	0.0000
	Inverse logit t (199)	L*	-6.0502	0.0000
S	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	6.9541	0.0000
	Inverse chi-squared (78)	P	183.9468	0.0000
	Inverse normal	Z	-6.5956	0.0000
	Inverse logit t (199)	L*	-6.815	0.0000
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	8.4825	0.0000

4.2.5 Fixed or Random Effects Model Test Results for Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Tables 4.6 DTA model with the moderator, the nulls were rejected at 5% risk level since the p values were 0.0063 respectively. This implies that fixed effects models were preferred. This implies that there is no correlation between the unobserved firm-specific random effects and the predictor's hence random effects model is preferred (Greene, 2008).

Table 4.6 Hausman Test Statistics for Non-Financial Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Model	Chi Square	D.f	P value
Without moderator	8.37	4	0.0789
With moderator	21.34	8	0.0063

4.2.6 Granger Causality Test Results for Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As earlier observed, the granger causality test is necessary to show which one between two variables explain the other one in a better manner (Granger, 1988). As shown in Table 4.7, the p-values for all lagged financial characteristics (in isolation) values and DTA, run against DTA, are greater than 5% level of significance. This implies that the null hypotheses that individual financial characteristic does not granger cause leverage are not rejected. When all lagged values of financial characteristics and DTA were run against DTA at the same time, the p value was zero. Being less than 5% level of significance, it means that the null hypothesis that financial characteristics do not granger causes leverage is rejected. Put otherwise, it means that the financial characteristics of a firm, as a combination but not in isolation, can explain its leverage. When the lagged values of DTA and individual financial characteristic were run against individual financial characteristics values at the same time, the p value for T and G were less than 5% level of significance. The p values for S and P were greater than the said significance level. This implies that for T and G, the null hypotheses that leverage does not granger cause tangibility and growth are rejected at a 5% significance level. In other words, leverage can explain firms' growth and tangibility but not performance and size. As cited in Mwangi (2016), the results contradict Dragota, Dragota, Obreja, and Semenescu (2008) who concluded that the null hypothesis of capital structure, measured by leverage, does not Granger cause profitability, a measure of performance, cannot be rejected.

Table 4.7 Granger Causality Test Statistics for Non-Financial Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable			
Dependent	Independent (Lagged)	F-statistic	p- value
DTA	S,DTA	1.48	0.2304
	T,DTA	2.21	0.0687
	P,DTA	2.08	0.0563
	G,DTA	1.59	0.1273

	S,T,P,G,DTA	50.81	0.0000
S	DTA,S	1.31	0.2708
T	DTA,T	3.66	0.0271
P	DTA,P	0.21	0.8090
G	DTA,G	4.48	0.0123

4.3 FGLS Regression Results with and without Moderator on the Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Leverage of Listed Non-financial Firms in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 4.8, results on the effect of financial characteristics on total debt financing while operating cash flow was incorporated in the model show that the coefficient of SCF was -0.017 hence firm sizes had a negative impact on total debt financing as operating cash flow increased. The p value was 0.012 which is less than 5% level of significance. This shows that the moderating effect of operating cash flow on firm size was statistically significant on total leverage. The coefficient of TCF was 0.121 hence tangibility had a positive effect on total leverage as operating cash flow increased. The p value was 0.084 which is greater than the 5% level of significance. This indicates that the moderating effect of operating cash flow on tangibility was statistically insignificant on debt financing.

The coefficients of PCF and GCF were 0.398 and -0.002 respectively. These indicate that profitability and growth opportunities had a positive and negative effect on total debt respectively when operating cash flow increased. The p values were 0 and 0.337 respectively to imply that the moderating effect of operating cash flow on profitability and growth opportunities were significant and insignificant respectively on total leverage at 5% level of significance. Overall, the moderating effect of operating cash flow on financial characteristics towards total leverage was 8.81% since the proportion of variation of total debt financing due to the variation in financing characteristics when the moderator was incorporated was 65.71%, compared with 56.9% without the moderator.

To further confirm the effect of the moderator, the coefficients of the model without the moderator are compared with the average marginal effect or change of financial characteristics on total leverage i.e.

$$\frac{\partial DTA_{it}}{\partial T_{it}} = \beta_1 + \beta_6 CF = 0.0245 - 0.16 * 0.017 = 0.022$$

$$\frac{\partial DTA_{it}}{\partial S_{it}} = \beta_2 + \beta_7 CF = -0.1362 + 0.16 * 0.122 = -0.116$$

$$\frac{\partial DTA_{it}}{\partial P_{it}} = \beta_3 + \beta_8 CF = 0.0011 - 0.16 * 0.0022 = 0.0106$$

$$\frac{\partial DTA_{it}}{\partial G_{it}} = \beta_4 + \beta_9 CF = 0.0004 + 0.16 * 0.398 = 0.064$$

When the above coefficients are compared with those of model 6, they are different implying that the operating cash flow has a moderating effect on the influence of firm financial characteristics and firms total leverage. An interesting observation is that the models with and without the moderator were significant at 5% level of significance. This shows that the financial characteristics, as well as a combination of the same with operating cash flow, are all good predictors of firm's leverage.

Table 4.8 FGLS Regression Results with and Without Moderator on the Influence of Financial Characteristics on Leverage of Listed Non-Financial Firms in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Without Moderation

With Moderation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z
cons	0.02	0.15	0.17	0.87	0.27	0.15	1.81	0.07
T	-0.05	0.07	-0.68	0.5	0.02	0.01	2.80	0.01
S	0.04	0.01	3.89	0	-0.14	0.06	-2.26	0.02
P	0.001	0.00	1.55	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.62
G	-0.0009	.0000	-0.27	0.78	0.00	0.00	0.32	0.75
CF					0.09	0.08	1.15	0.25
TCF					-0.02	0.01	-2.52	0.01
SCF					0.12	0.07	1.73	0.08
PCF					0.40	0.11	3.49	0.00
GCF					0.00	0.00	-0.96	0.34
	Wald chi ² (4) =0.0029	R ² = 0.569		P > Chi ² 0.00	Wald chi ² (9) =75.68	R ² = 0.6571		p>Chi ² .0000

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the study findings it is paramount to note that firm financial characteristics have a significant influence on the leverage of non-financial listed companies in NSE. The study concludes that increased short term borrowing is associated with increased tangibility amongst listed non-financial companies in NSE. Similarly, non-financial listed company's long borrowing capacity was accelerated with increased asset tangibility. In contrast, increased tangibility had decreased non-financial listed companies borrowing capacity. Consequently, listed non-financial companies should continuously evaluate leverage covenants prior to the acquisition of new loans so as to maximize on debt covenants which they enter into.

The study established isolation on the choice of leverage due to firm characteristics. In some instances, some characteristics had a significant influence on either short-term debt, long term debt and or total debt. Consequently, non-financial listed companies in NSE should combine both short term and long-term debt. In addition, to this debt covenants ought to be negotiated after collective consideration of firm characteristics and none ought to be considered in isolation of others. It is thus paramount for both financial managers and financial analysts to continuously monitor firm characteristics through of requisite data science tools and evaluate the robustness of alternative financing option in regard to specific firm characteristics. This way firm's survivability will be enhanced since chances of bad debt can be easily mitigated.

References

- i. *Acheampong, P., Agalega, E., & Shibu, K. (2014). The Effect of Financial Leverage and Market Size on Stock Returns on the Ghana Stock Exchange: Evidence from Selected Stocks in the Manufacturing Sector. International Journal of Financial Research, 5(1), 125-134.*
- ii. *Addae, A., Nyarko-Baasi, M., & Hughes, D. (2013). The Effects of Capital Structure on Profitability of Listed Firms in Ghana, European Journal of Business and Management, 5 (31), 215-229.*
- iii. *Badar, R., & Saeed, A. (2013). Impact of Capital Structure on Performance Empirical Evidence from Sugar Sector of Pakistan, European Journal of Business and Management, 5 (5): 78-86.*
- iv. *Chesang, D., & Ayuma, O. (2016). Effect of Financial Leverage on Profitability of Listed Agricultural Firms at the Nairobi Securities Exchange, International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management, 4(12),445-493.*

- v. Ezeoha, A. E. (2008). *Firm size and corporate financial leverage choice in a developing economy: Evidence from Nigeria*, *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 9(4), 351-364.
- vi. Gathogo, G., & Ragui, M. (2014). *Capital Structure of Kenyan Firms: What determines it?* *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(5), 118-125.
- vii. Githira, C. W., & Nasieku, T. (2015). *Capital Structure Determinants among Companies Quoted in Securities Exchange in East Africa*, *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(5), 483-496.
- viii. Granger, C. W. (1988). *Causality, Cointegration, and Control*. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 12(3), 551-559.
- ix. Greene, W. H. (2008). *The Econometric Approach to Efficiency Analysis. The Measurement of Productive Efficiency and Productivity growth*, Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu> on 5/8/2017.
- x. Gujarati, D. (2003). *Basic Econometrics (4th Ed.)*. New York: McGraw Hill.
- xi. Handoo, A., & Sharma, K. (2014). *A study on Determinants of Capital Structure in India*, *IIMB Management Review*, 14(26), 170-182.
- xii. Handoo, A., & Sharma, K. (2014). *A study on Determinants of Capital Structure in India*, *IIMB Management Review*, 14(26), 170-182.
- xiii. Hasannejadneisi, S., Mazraeh, S., & Mousavi, Z. (2013). *Evaluating the Relationship between Firm Characteristics and Financial Leverage*, *Journal of Novel Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 978-981.
- xiv. Ikechukwu, I. O., & Madubuko, C. (2016). *Effect of Firm Size on Corporate Borrowing of Oil and Gas Firms in Nigeria*, *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 4(5), 303-308.
- xv. Mahnazmahdavi, M., Mokhtarbaseri, M., Zare, A. & Zare, H. (2013). *The Effect of Sales Growth on the Determinants of Capital Structure of Listed Companies in Tehran Stock Exchange*. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 7(2), 306-311.
- xvi. Muchiri, M. J., Muturi, W. M., & Ngumi, P. M. (2016). *Relationship between Financial Structure and Financial Performance of Firms Listed at East Africa Securities Exchanges*. *Journal of Emerging Issues in Economics, Finance and Banking* 5(1), 1734-1755.
- xvii. Mwangi, J. M. (2016). *Effect of Financial Structure on Financial Performance of Firms Listed at East Africa Securities Exchanges, (PHD Thesis)*, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, School of Business, Nairobi, Kenya.
- xviii. Mwangi, L. W., Makau, M. S., & Kosimbei, G. (2014). *Relationship between Capital Structure and Performance of Non-Financial Companies Listed in the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Kenya*. *Global Journal of Contemporary Research in Accounting, Auditing and Business Ethics*, 1(2), 72-90.
- xix. Mwangi, M., & Birundu, E. M. (2015). *The Effect of Capital Structure on the Financial Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Thika Sub-County, Kenya*, *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 5(1), 151-156.

- xx. *Tai, L. M. (2017). Impact of the Financial Markets Development on Capital Structure of Firms Listed on Ho Chi Minh Stock Exchange. International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues, 7(3), 510-515.*
- xxi. *Tarus, T. K., Chenous, N., & Biwott, G. (2014). Do Profitability, Firm Size and Liquidity Affect Capital Structure? Evidence from Kenyan Listed Firms, European Journal of Business and Management, 6(28), 119-124.*
- xxii. *Wahome, M. N., Memba, F., & Muturi, W. (2015). The Effects of Firm Size and Risk on Capital Structure Decisions of Insurance Industry in Kenya, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, 5(8),1-12.*
- xxiii. *Wooldridge, J. M. (2002). Econometric Analysis of Cross Section and Panel Data. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.*